

INTEGRATED, TRANSDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH FOR THE AGROECOLOGICAL TRANSITION

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About this brief

European agriculture stands at a critical crossroads, facing mounting pressures from climate change, biodiversity loss, and emerging threats to plant, animal, and human health. These challenges threaten the sustainability and resilience of our food systems and rural communities.

To address these urgent needs and secure a healthy future for all, the AgroServ project has been implementing **integrated, transdisciplinary research-based solutions that drive the transition toward sustainable and resilient agricultural systems across Europe.**

By integrating leading European Research Infrastructures, AgroServ offers researchers worldwide **access to a comprehensive portfolio** of tools and services designed to drive innovation across the agricultural sector and its related fields.

These services support the rapid analysis of agronomic practices, enable the assessment of threats such as climate change and emerging pests, and facilitate the evaluation of the socio-economic dimensions of sustainable transitions—fully aligned with the One Health approach. Complementing and building upon transnational access, **AgroServ's Living Labs** play a critical role in bridging scientific knowledge with real-world application. Through iterative, stakeholder-driven collaboration, the Living Labs connect diverse users, innovations, and regional contexts, ensuring that research output is not only scientifically sound but also practical, inclusive, and tailored to the complex realities of Europe's agroecosystems.

The AgroServ Innovation Model

Transdisciplinary: tackling complex, cross-cutting questions on one subject –agroecology– that spans large scientific domains.

Transnational: leveraging the collective strengths of 11 Research Infrastructures (RIs) –major organizations spanning diverse scientific fields – to provide services at the European scale.

Transformative: focusing on service provision for real-world challenges, enabling both researchers and society to benefit from innovation.

AgroServ unites 11 leading RIs to deliver integrated, transdisciplinary services that address the urgent challenges facing agriculture and food systems. This collective approach empowers researchers and stakeholders to access advanced tools, data, and expertise for real-world impact.

AgroServ represents a methodological breakthrough in the European research infrastructure landscape around sustainable agriculture by moving beyond siloed research and fostering true transdisciplinary integration in practice.

By integrating more than 140 services and stimulating interdisciplinary projects, AgroServ supports challenge-driven research and innovation. The integrated offer of services from European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) and further pan-European RIs is continuously updated based on user feedback, ensuring that services remain relevant and impactful in the project lifespan and beyond.

This policy document has been approved by the AgroServ Executive Committee. It does not necessarily reflect the views of all AgroServ partners.

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AgroServ's contribution towards EU Policy

AgroServ's mission is fully aligned with the EU Green Deal, Farm to Fork Strategy, Food 2030 and complements HE research and innovation programmes, particularly the Agroecology Partnership.

The project responds to these European policy priorities by:

- Accelerating climate-neutral and resource-efficient agriculture:** through advanced monitoring, modelling, and field platforms, AgroServ supports efforts to lower greenhouse gas emissions, increase soil carbon storage, and optimize resource use.
- Enabling biodiversity conservation and restoration:** integrated infrastructures allow research on ecosystem health, with a focus on supporting pollinators, conserving soils, and fostering biodiversity across farming systems.
- Reducing agrochemical inputs:** AgroServ's services make available experimental and analytical resources for developing nature-based pest and nutrient management, facilitating Farm to Fork targets of halving pesticide risk and nutrient loss by 2030.
- Advancing sustainable food systems:** by supporting research into resilient crop rotations, new food sources, and robust traceability, AgroServ helps deliver food systems that are healthier, more affordable, and environmentally sound.
- Fostering socio-economic viability and inclusive innovation:** tools for socio-economic research and co-designed living labs ensure SMEs and stakeholders are actively involved in developing impactful solutions, strengthening rural communities and value chains.
- Driving digital and infrastructural innovation:** harmonised data platforms and remote sensing capabilities lay the groundwork for precision agriculture and better policy-making across the EU.

By aligning its services and innovation pathway with these core research themes, AgroServ provides direct and measurable contributions to **the EU's vision for a sustainable, climate-resilient, and competitive agri-food sector by 2030 and beyond.**

Moreover, AgroServ provides a unique framework and expertise required to establish and connect with living labs¹, complementing the effort of the Agroecology Partnership with its European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures.

The key distinction—and complementarity—between AgroServ and the AELLRI partnership lies in their orientation: **AgroServ is science- and user-driven**, whereas the Partnership reflects the priorities of its national founders. Looking ahead, AgroServ also interacts closely with INFRATECH projects such as PHENET, driving innovation and the development of next generation of future agroecology services across Europe.

	AgroServ	Agroecology Partnership
Core Objective	Integrates and offers access to research infrastructures (RIs) for transnational and transdisciplinary agroecology research.	Coordinates living labs and RIs to accelerate the Europe-wide transition to agroecology through site-specific innovation and practice.
Duration & Funding	2022–2027, Horizon Europe, €14M, 73 partners.	2024–2030, Horizon Europe, €300M, 72 partners
Main activities	RI services for plant, animal, soil & human health; living labs; transdisciplinary data ecosystem; free transnational access calls.	Network of living labs, policy-science dialogue, practice assessment, webinars/masterclasses, indicator/tool development, capacity building
Approach	User-driven, responds to stakeholder and applicants' priorities; multi-actor co-creation across the research process (strong focus on service delivery).	Place-based, long-term, multi-stakeholder real-life experimentation; mainstreams agroecology into policy/practice and develops methodologies for transition evaluation.
Target Beneficiaries	Researchers, farmers, SMEs, policy makers, agri-food sector, rural communities.	Farmers, researchers, policy makers, local authorities, producer organizations.
Scale & Coverage	Pan-European catalogue offer with international applicants to the TNA programme, cross-sector coverage encompassing multiple environmental and socio-economic goals.	Pan-European, landscape-wide focus, supports long-term agroecological transformation with monitoring and capacity building.
Distinctive Features	Service pipelines, experimental simulation, policy support, FAIR/open data, evidence synthesis, and innovation impact.	Development and deployment of Living Labs, transformative and practice-based change, direct support for farmers.

Table: AgroServ and the Agroecology Partnership, a summary

Towards 2050

The provision and design of research services [initiates projects](#) that can evolve into lasting initiatives, aligning with and supporting the Agroecology Partnership's 2050 [vision](#) for sustainable food systems and a thriving agricultural sector

AgroServ calls for **continued investments in integrated Research Infrastructures** that enable transdisciplinary and transnational collaboration. The support of challenge-driven, user-oriented services is also paramount to **ensure research meets real-world needs, keeping Europe competitive in the agri-food sector.** Finally, **fostering long-term partnerships and feedback mechanisms** is key to continuous improvement of collaborative research, aiming at a sustainable agroecological transition.

By advancing these priorities, **Europe can lead the way in sustainable agriculture**, ensuring projects like AgroServ deliver **lasting benefits for society, the environment, and the economy.**

ADVANCING SUSTAINABILITY WITH AGROSERV AND SMES

In Central Italy, Alberto Akiki –a PhD candidate from IUSS Pavia and the University of Teramo under the supervision of Prof. Giampiero Sacchetti– led a project to **valorize the emmer wheat supply chain** and validate its sustainability. By collaborating with local food businesses and leveraging AgroServ's Catalogue of Services, Akiki was able to streamline his research and achieve impactful results:

- Advanced analyses and novel methodologies:** Akiki accessed AgroServ's Research Infrastructures to perform nutritional and functional characterization, develop prototypes, and conduct socio-economic surveys, enabling a comprehensive assessment of emmer wheat's value
- Transdisciplinary collaboration:** the project brought together expertise from three different RIs, spanning multiple scientific domains, to evaluate both the sustainability and functionality of emmer wheat-based foods.
- SMEs partnership:** working closely with small and medium-sized enterprises in the agri-food sector, Akiki explored the societal, economic, nutritional, and functional benefits of emmer wheat, directly contributing to more sustainable food systems and supporting local economies.

AgroServ has become an important stepstone for my career, offering free access to further research units, and enhancing the project's accountability

— Alberto Akiki

¹ the AgroServ Living Labs approach is explored in a recent [policy brief](#)